

**“They jump out of planes and drive tanks”
- A Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis of Women in the German
Armed Forces (Bundeswehr) Digital Recruitment Campaigns
(2022–2025)**

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Abstract: Research on how the German Armed Forces (*Bundeswehr*) seek to recruit women remains limited, despite women currently accounting for 13.63 % of the force. This master’s thesis examines how digital recruitment content targeting women between 2022 and 2025 reproduces or challenges gendered framings of women’s military participation. Drawing on a Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis (FVNA), the study analyses $n = 212$ posts and videos published on the *Bundeswehr*’s official YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok channels. The findings show that recruitment content simultaneously increases women’s visibility while continuing to reproduce militarised masculine norms. Women framed as “successfully” integrated soldiers are further positioned as symbolic exceptions (“Tokens”). This potentially undermines women’s military participation and might contribute to the persistently low representation of women within the *Bundeswehr*.

Keywords: Gender; Bundeswehr; Digital Recruitment; Visual Narratives; Women’s Military Participation

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Abbreviations:

AF	– Armed Forces
BMVg	– <i>Bundesministerium für Verteidigung</i> (Germany's Federal Ministry of Defence)
Bw	– <i>Bundeswehr</i> (German Armed Forces)
CDU	– <i>Christlich Demokratische Union</i> (Christian Democratic Union)
DT	– Discursive Tokenism
ECJ	– European Court of Justice
EU	– European Union
FETs	– Female Engagement Teams
FSS	– Feminist Security Studies
FNVA	– Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis
GG	– <i>Grundgesetz</i> (Germany's Constitution)
JIM	– <i>Jugend, Information, Medien Study</i> (Youth, Information, Media Study)
KSK	– <i>Kommando Spezialkräfte</i> (German Special Forces)
MAXQDA	– Qualitative Data Analysis Software
NATO	– North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
RQ	– Research Question
SEDU	– Swedish Defence University (<i>Försvarshögskolan</i>)
SgleiG	– <i>Soldatinnen-Gleichstellungsgesetz</i> (Soldiers' Law of Equality)
SPD	– <i>Sozialdemokratische Partei Deutschlands</i> (Social Democratic Party of Germany)
WMP	– Women's Military Participation
ZIF	– <i>Zentrum Innere Führung</i> (Centre for Inner Leadership)

Key Terms:

To be conceptually concise in this thesis, the following key terms are understood the following:

Gender: Refers here to the social construction of categories (i.e. men and women) that derive from “female” and “male” bodies (see Cohn 2013, 7). This construction orders social practices (Connell 2021, 71) through the normative attributions of masculinity and femininity to the respective sex (see Cohn 2013, 6).

Femininity and Masculinity: The table is based on Cohn (2013, 6), outlining the most prevalent gendered attributions of masculinity and femininity:

Table 1: Gendered Attributions of Masculinity and Femininity

ATTRIBUTE:	MASCULINITY	FEMININITY
DESCRIPTION:	<i>Stronger, more rational, controlled in emotions, smarter, independent, tougher, better decision-makers, courageous, more aggressive and willing to fight, achievement-driven, world shapers (public life).</i>	<i>Weaker, irrational, governed by emotions, less intelligent, dependent, soft, indecisive, timid, passive, bad at math and science, private over public life.</i>

Hegemonic Masculinity: The dominant and idealised form of masculinity in a society. Its primary function is to justify and maintain patriarchy, ensuring the social dominance of men and the continued subordination of women (Connell 2021, 77).

Patriarchy: A social system characterised by the dominance of men and the subordination of women. This system allocates more resources, power, and authority to men (see Cockburn 2010, 142ff.; Cohn 2013, 4; Connell 2021, 85).

Women soldiers: This term is used instead of “female soldiers” to emphasise gender (the social construct) over sex (the biological distinction). Choosing “female soldier” in this thesis would imply a natural, inherent difference from a (male) “soldier,” thereby neglecting the effects of the social attributions of masculinity and femininity.

Women’s Military Participation is understood as women soldiers’ participation in their respective functions within the AF (see Carreiras 2006, 13ff.).

Women’s Underrepresentation and “Tokenism”: Women Soldiers are visible as underrepresented if they make up less than 40 % within the AF. They are seen as “Tokens” if they make less than 15 % within the AF (see Kanter 1977, 383ff.).

Tokens: A token is a visual representative, in distinction from the dominant group (i.e., men soldiers), making the “token” overly visible while pressuring the tokenised group with a distinct set of role expectations and evaluations compared to the dominant group (ibid.).

1. Introduction

1.1. Setting the Stage: The Bundeswehr's Rhetoric / Reality Disconnect

The German Armed Forces (henceforth *Bundeswehr*) paints a compelling picture of gender equality and successful integration of women into its forces:

They fly combat aircraft and helicopters. They jump out of planes and drive tanks. They command naval ships and line companies. [...]. Servicewomen have now made their way into almost every area of what once was a man's world (own translation¹, Bundeswehr 2025a).

Women make up 13.63 % (24,947 soldiers) of the armed forces (AF) (Bundeswehr 2025a; Bundestag 2025c), a significant discrepancy to the 20 % threshold for women in military roles set by the German Soldiers' Law of Equality (*Soldatinnen- und Soldatengleichstellungsgesetz*) (SGleiG 2024)². The low representation of women in the Bundeswehr is seen as a product of dominant masculine cultures (see Kümmel 2008, 5; 2014a, 68; 2015, 85f.).

Nevertheless, since 2001, when women were allowed to join the Bundeswehr, this hegemonic ideal has institutionally shifted to who is considered the more "effective" soldier (i.e. masculine men). Despite this, the Bundeswehr maintains explicit recruitment efforts, interpreted as targeting women, noticeable in the $n=212$ sources analysed in this thesis.

This effort was previously also visible in the "Join the Team" (*Komm in die Mannschaft*)³ campaign — a spot recently removed from the official YouTube channel. This contradiction between the Bundeswehr's institutional rhetoric of "successful integration" and its recruitment efforts into "what once was a man's world," and the functional reality of legal underrepresentation, constitutes the central research puzzle of this thesis. Consequently, this analysis seeks to demonstrate that the organisation's messaging on social media (YouTube, Instagram and TikTok) reproduces particular images of women soldiers, contributing to the sustained failure to achieve successful recruitment and integration of women.

The following section will contextualise this puzzle by examining the historical and legal forces that brought women into the Bundeswehr.

¹ **Note:** Until stated otherwise, all German sources have been translated by the author. This also applies to all quotes from the analysed dataset ($n=212$). To improve readability, individual translations are not marked. This applies solely to German sources, as the author is a native speaker of the language.

² **Note:** The SGleiG was amended in 2023, defining women as underrepresented if they make up less than 20% in military roles, 30% when including civilian positions, and 50 % in medical service roles (§3 (5) SGleiG 2024). Except for the overall share, the goals are not met, as the last parliamentary report states (see Bundestag 2025c).

³ @BundeswehrExclusive: *Komm in Die Mannschaft*. (0:29). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wXd5noeRyxs>. (Last access: 22.09.2025; removed during the writing of this thesis)

1.2. The Tanja Kreil v. Federal Republic of Germany ECJ Judgment (2000)

Tanja Kreil's 1996 application to become a weapon technician for the Bundeswehr was rejected under the prevailing German legal framework, specifically Article 12a(4) of the German Constitution: *Grundgesetz (GG)*. It reserved all military combat roles for men, allowing women to join the medical and military music services only (Liebert 2002, 3f.). The rejection led to the landmark judgment by the European Court of Justice (ECJ) in *Tanja Kreil v Bundesrepublik Deutschland* (2000). As a result, Germany could no longer legally justify an all-male Bundeswehr, as this contravened European Union (EU) equality law, particularly Article 2(1) and (2) of Directive 76/207/EEC (*ibid.*). This — legally enforced — “manoeuvre”, as Cynthia Enloe (2000, 45) would term it, was met with ambiguity between policy implementation, public opinion about women in the Bundeswehr and internal organisational resistance (see Apelt 2002, 325ff.; Apelt, Dittmer, and Mangold 2005, 118f.; Ahrens, Apelt, and Bender 2004; Kümmel 2008; 2014a; 2015; Dossall 2021, 456ff.). Although women have been allowed to serve in any military role since 2001 (*ibid.*), this is true only in theory, as will be discussed in Chapter 5.3.

1.3. Russia, Kriegstüchtigkeit and the Current Imperative for Extended Recruitment Efforts

The Bundeswehr's reputation as an underfunded, poorly equipped, and campaign-incapable force is rooted in a prolonged period of post-World War II political caution and post-reunification stagnation (see Dalgaard-Nielsen 2013). This path-dependency led to reluctance to increase defence spending, which limited the Bundeswehr's equipment and readiness due to the “peace dividend⁴” after reunification and the end of the Cold War (see Bardt 2021, 52f.). Coined the *Zeitenwende* (change of times) by former Chancellor Olaf Scholz (SPD) (Bundestag 2022), this geopolitical rupture led to a €100 billion special fund for the Bundeswehr's rearmament. It established a new, militarising strategic goal: *Kriegstüchtigkeit* (war preparedness) (Federal Ministry of Defence [BMVg] 2023). The rhetoric of *Kriegstüchtigkeit* — or the militarisation of the AF and militarism in society (see Cockburn 2010, 139) — has been coined by Minister of Defence Boris Pistorius (SPD) (BMVg 2023; 2025). War preparedness on a larger scale contributes to the societal normalisation of the possibility of war against Russia. In light of this shared threat perception, Sweden and Finland joined the *North Atlantic Treaty Organisation* (NATO) (see Forsberg and Christiansson 2025). In Germany, *Kriegstüchtigkeit* is framed in neo-realist terms of conventional deterrence, following

⁴ **Note:** The “peace dividend” refers to the reallocation of public funds away from defense expenditure toward social and economic sectors, following the downsizing of the Bundeswehr after the Cold War.

the *si vis pacem, para bellum* (If you want peace, prepare for war) logic. For the Bundeswehr, this requires a massive personnel boost, moving from 181,514 active soldiers to 260,000 active soldiers and 200,000 reservists by 2035 (Die Zeit 2025), aiming to fulfil NATO strategy commitments (ibid.). The ambition of what Chancellor Friedrich Merz (CDU) envisions as “the strongest conventional Army in Europe” (Bundestag 2025b) is in tension with the current reality of the Bundeswehr’s women’s recruitment capacity.

Despite the legal requirement since 2001 and the 2023 political targets, the Bundeswehr continues to struggle with women’s recruitment. Despite being a political problem, this is also a strategic concern for achieving the *Kriegstüchtigkeit* aim. To address the personnel needs, the BMVg prepared for the reactivation of an adapted conscription policy informed by the “Swedish Model” (see CDU / CSU and SPD 2025, 130). On December 5th, 2025, the German Parliament (*Bundestag*) voted in favour of a new voluntary conscription model. Men turning 18 will receive a survey to be answered by providing personal data (Bundestag 2025a). Due to the need for a two-thirds majority to amend Article 12a of the constitution, the Bundestag will not vote to amend to allow for the conscription of women (see Bundeswehr 2025c).

Women consequently do not need to answer the drafting letter (Bundestag 2025a). This political constraint effectively sidelines the debate over mandatory women’s recruitment, leaving voluntary enlistment as the only current path for women to join the Bundeswehr. This path effectively places the entire burden of meeting personnel quotas onto women’s successful recruitment. This forces the Bundeswehr to *visually represent* women in a way that overcomes existing societal and institutional gender barriers to be successful in this target group. A 2008 in-house study of the Bundeswehr stated that women’s recruitment potential was between 15 % and 20 % (Kümmel 2008, 14). According to ZDFheute (2025), the women’s share of applications has indeed risen to 16 %, yet dropout rates within the first 6 months remain relatively high (ZDFheute 2025; Bundestag 2025c, 81ff.).

Groh from the *Bundeswehr University Munich*, on the contrary, opposes the idea of women’s conscription as it fails to address existing societal gender inequalities like unequal care work and pay. This, consequently, would add a legal burden to women’s already disadvantaged position (Groh in mdr.de 2025). Nevertheless, this is not an argument against increased recruitment of women into the Bundeswehr. Nevertheless, the debate on conscripting women as “only [...] the fourth step” (Tagesschau 2025), as stated by Chancellor Merz, indicates a tendency to avoid a general gender equality debate. For the Bundeswehr, this gender-sidelining is communicated by the initial quote that women already successfully perform demanding

combat duties like “jumping out of planes and driving tanks.” This narrative can be analysed as a discursive manoeuvre (see Enloe 2000, 45) — a positive framing of persistent structural resistance, visible in another puzzling paradox: While Germany pursues a conscription model inspired by Sweden, it completely sidelines its gender-neutral premise. Sweden’s model is based on compulsory *gender-neutral* enrolment and selection (see Persson and Sundevall 2019, 1042). By focusing only on men’s conscription, Germany is adopting the mechanism but deliberately ignores the gender-equalising strategic intent. A leaked internal memo by Lieutenant-General Mais expressed scepticism that the Bundeswehr will reach its overall *Zeitenwende* personnel targets. The intent to increase women's recruitment has not been stated in the memo (Mais 2025; Politico 2025), underscoring the political nature of this issue. The internal memo, combined with the political prioritisation of men’s conscription, confirms the persistent marginalisation of women’s recruitment debate, which remains trapped in a contradiction: While more women have joined the Bundeswehr since 2001, policy quotas of the SGleiG and recruitment potentials are still unmatched. This demonstrates the need to analyse the institutional effort to recruit women more thoroughly. Therefore, this thesis expects to find a part of this puzzle in the visible online recruitment material published by the Bundeswehr itself.

1.4. From Research Puzzle to Research Question: Digital Recruitment Campaigns Targeting Women

To make sense of this ambiguity between women’s recruitment failure and success, this thesis demonstrates that there is an internal, often overlooked aspect of militarised hegemonic masculinity, emergent through visual recruitment material. Building on this contextual background and the identified puzzle, the central **research question (RQ)** is: *To what extent do Bundeswehr social media campaigns (2022–2025) targeting women reproduce or challenge gendered framings of women’s soldiership?*

1.5. Scope and object of this thesis

The object of this research is defined by time and media. The selected timeframe (2022–2025) is crucial because the full-scale invasion of Ukraine marked the beginning of the *Zeitenwende* discourse (see Blumenau 2022; Fröhlich 2023). The scope is limited to analysing micro-level visual representations produced by the Bundeswehr’s official digital recruitment channels (i.e., YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok). This analysis excludes an in-depth examination of media reception of potential recruits, focusing instead on the organisational, externalised communication itself.

1.6. Contribution and objective of this thesis

Motivated by the central research puzzle and guiding research question, the primary objective of this thesis is to identify patterns evident in digital recruitment materials that may contribute to the persistently low share of women soldiers in the Bundeswehr. This research provides a novel contribution by leveraging the contemporary discourses of the *Zeitenwende* and *Kriegstüchtigkeit* to assess the potential lack of proportional attention to gender equality in a time of renewed war preparedness.

Methodologically, this thesis seeks to bridge a gap in existing scholarship by employing a Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis (FVNA). This approach is situated within the field of Feminist Security Studies (FSS) and is a novel application of FSS methodology to the case of the Bundeswehr's video recruitment material.

1.7. Structure of the Thesis:

This thesis is divided into six main chapters, following the design of a classic academic structure (Roselle and Spray 2012, 47):

- **Chapter 1 (Introduction):** Introduced the research puzzle, contextualised the study within the *Zeitenwende / Kriegstüchtigkeit discourses*, stated the RQ, and defined the scope and objectives of this thesis.
- **Chapter 2 (Self-Reflexivity):** Acknowledges the role the author plays in the interpretivist endeavour of this thesis, offering personal insights about privileges and positionality shaping the design and interpretation of findings in this thesis.
- **Chapter 3 (Literature Review):** Situates the research within the fields of Feminist Security Studies (FSS), critical visual analysis, and existing scholarship on the *Bundeswehr*.
- **Chapter 4 (Research Design):** Outlines the methodological approach, detailing the feminist research methodology and the specific method of Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis (FVNA).
- **Chapter 5 (Analysis and Discussion):** Presents the core analysis of the Bundeswehr's digital recruitment material through three emergent strategic dynamics of *Discursive Tokenism* (I; II–III; IV).
- **Chapter 6 (Conclusion):** Summarises the key findings, answers the RQ, and suggests avenues for future research.

2. Self-Reflexivity, Authorial Privilege and Positionality

Being a male (he/him) student at the Swedish Defence University (SEDU) — a rather masculinised environment comprising both civilian and military personnel — my engagement with feminist and gender-related concepts often invites scepticism. However, the “Gender, Peace, and Security” group at the SEDU provides an academic forum for critical thought on gender and, i.e. AF. I had the privilege of attending engaging meetings with scholars working on gender-related topics. On the contrary, when discussing my thesis, I also frequently encountered amused or dismissive reactions from some civilian men at the SEDU, who implied there were “more important” topics for research. These encounters ranged from a civilian student sarcastically questioning the integration of women: “Is that even a good thing?” — to another mockingly stating that Germany’s low share of women in the AF “is the reason why you guys can defend yourself.” On another occasion, I found myself subconsciously hiding my pride-coloured lanyard in the men’s locker room, an act I interpreted as an embodied response to the place’s unspoken norms of masculinity. Self-critically, I realise this reflects a subconscious fear of being labelled “too woke” or gay and consequently being judged for something that should not be worth mentioning. Since there is no natural reason to feel excluded for wearing a lanyard, the inherently implicit nature of this norm, true or not, illustrates my ontological position that these conventions and institutions are socially constructed. This feeling is thus not rooted in direct confrontative experiences, but in the subtle, institutional scepticism fuelled by observing misogynist and sexist locker room “talks.”

My own position is nonetheless marked by intersecting privileges, which require ethical awareness. My status as a cisgender man, along with my sexuality, white ethnicity, educational background, and civilian status at SEDU, is privileged. This is exemplified by the fact that I had the choice to mitigate discomfort by simply hiding a gendered symbol or choosing not to talk openly about my thesis. In contrast, this option for immediate discretion is not readily available to women or those with non-normative gender expressions; my experiences are therefore never comparable to the discrimination women and others face. In this light, writing this reflection feels easier — more privileged — than it should, echoing Cynthia Enloe’s observation that “self-reflexivity shouldn’t be easy” (Enloe 2016, 258). Therefore, it is both methodologically and ethically sound to engage openly with inseparably identity-based biases, as they have shaped this thesis from its conceptual beginnings through to its final form (see, for example, interpretivist and feminist research ethics: Ackerly and True 2008; 2018; Fujii 2012; Wibben 2016b, 11; Zulver 2021, 445f.; Axyonova and Lozka 2023; Anctil Avoine 2024,

1662f.; Martín De Almagro et al. 2024). I further acknowledge that the military, despite its ambivalent gender relations, is a highly relevant professional actor in human and national security. While gender relations within the AF might not appear to be “the most important” matter during times of geopolitical turmoil, I contend that the engagement of women and other marginalised groups is precisely what matters in times of crisis, as historically proven by their increased participation in wars (see Hacker 1981; Kemnitz 1998; Carreiras 2006; Zaliotok 2024). I am aware that merely “adding women and stir[ring]” (Zalewski 1993, 15) is insufficient (see Carreiras 2006, 126ff.). Nevertheless, unlike some fellow male students, I believe that adding women, when accompanied by organisational change, will not only enhance strategic defence capabilities but will also tangibly improve the lives of women within the AF.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Feminist Security Studies, Gender and the Military

Drawing from the foundational critique of scholars like Cohn (1987; 1993; 2013) and Cockburn (2004; 2010), Feminist Security Studies (FSS) emerged as a critical response to the gender-blindness of traditional security studies i.e., War studies (see, for instance, Tickner 1988; Zalewski 1993; Gentry 2009, 240ff.; Sjoberg 2010; Sylvester 2013, 49f.; Wibben 2016b, 61ff.; Connell 2021, 68–86). The academic institutionalisation of FSS — particularly through emerging peace research — led to a strong anti-militarist orientation, which in turn created tensions between mainstream and critical security studies (see Enloe 2004, 22; 2014, 15ff.).

FSS bridges peace and security studies by positioning gender as a key analytical category within the intersectional⁵ analysis by asking explicitly feminist questions (Sylvester 2013, 6ff.; Wibben 2016b, 71). The study of militarism, defined as a “persisting mindset of war readiness” (Cockburn 2010, 148), remains central to feminist questions, as underscored by the *Zeitenwende* and *Kriegstüchtigkeit* discourses. Feminist questions challenge dominant security narratives and open new spaces for understanding gendered power relations within militarised structures, an idea behind this thesis's RQ. Feminist scholars have examined how militaries — as hegemonic masculine institutions — construct, constrain, and occasionally incorporate gendered bodies (see Herbert 1998; Hooper 2001, 10ff.; Hutchings 2008; MacKenzie 2015). Hacker (1981), for instance, demonstrates that women already played a vital role in Western AF from the 14th to the 19th century. Elshtain (1995) further argues that women combatants

⁵ **Note:** For intersectionality, see Crenshaw (1989). For a critique on its application see Henry (2017, 183).

are often perceived as “unnatural,” a view echoed by Alison (2004, 457), who notes that women’s violence is seen as particularly disturbing because it challenges patriarchal gender norms (see also Åhäll 2015, 8ff.). Enloe (2007), on the other hand, argues that studying women’s roles in the military can risk legitimising the institution itself, potentially sidelining critical engagement with militarism by normalising women's experiences in the AF (see, for a critique of military masculinities, Zalewski 2017). Nevertheless, as Sjoberg (2010, 602) argues, the purpose of FSS research is: “to raise problems, not to solve them; to draw attention to a field of inquiry, rather than survey it fully; to provoke discussion, rather than serve as a systematic treatise.” FSS research, therefore, must examine the realities of women’s participation in military institutions, as women are already part of them. In keeping with this mandate of “drawing attention” to women in the Bundeswehr, the next chapter will show that this has not been done sufficiently yet.

3.2. Existing research on women in the Bundeswehr and gender-neutral service

While women in Western AF are generally a well-researched subject, particularly concerning the US military (see Wibben 2016a; 2016b; 2018; Planiol 2016; Miller 2024), there is insufficient attention to the Bundeswehr when it comes to women soldiers, especially when considering women’s historical military engagement in German AFs⁶ (see Kemnitz 1998, 69-82; Zalietok 2024, 18-24). Dedicated feminist, or FSS-led research, is thus almost nonexistent. An exception to the gender-blindness in studying the Bundeswehr is the two Bundeswehr studies by Kümmel (2008; 2014a), including a survey of 5300 soldiers (male and female). The studies explicitly focus on the effects of women’s integration into the Bundeswehr, concluding that internal resistance to the inclusion of women in the Bundeswehr is often based on stereotypical and essentialising prejudices about women (Kümmel 2008, 103ff.; 2014b, 67ff.). While the “climate of integration” has increased somewhat, it has done so insufficiently (ibid.). This ambiguity represents a common finding in the literature (see Apelt 2002, 331; Apelt, Dittmer, and Mangold 2005, 118ff. ; Ahrens, Apelt, and Bender 2004, 23; Kümmel 2015; Dodsall 2021; Graf and Kümmel 2022, 948f.). Further, two notable papers offer a more intersectional, critical analysis: Näser-Lather (2018) examines contemporary discourses on homosexuality in the Bundeswehr, while Gashi and Hendrich (2023) examine Women of Colour’s experiences within the Bundeswehr. These studies may be the closest to the field of

⁶ **Note:** Kemnitz (1998) and Zalietok (2024) refer to the following historical German AF: *Deutsches Heer* (1871–1918); the *Wehrmacht* (1935–1945); the *Bundeswehr* (West Germany, 1955 – present); and the *Nationale Volksarmee* (East Germany, 1956–1990).

FSS currently available, even if they do not position themselves within it. The gender-research gap in the German case is particularly notable compared to other AF, such as the Swedish Armed Forces, which benefit from extensive scholarship reflecting the Swedish self-image as a “bastion of gender equality” (see Persson and Sundevall 2019, 1040). Given this contrast and the Bundeswehr’s own low representation of women soldiers, the following chapter will establish the theoretical foundation and framework — employing Kanter’s (1977) theoretical concept of “Tokenism” — to analyse the gender dynamics within the German forces and build the methodological basis for this thesis.

4. Research Design

4.1. Theoretical foundation: Kanter’s theory of “Tokenism” located in the Women’s Military Participation Framework

This research is grounded in a social constructivist ontology (see Harding 1986; Schwartz-Shea and Yanow 2012, 38). More specifically, this thesis understands the social world as governed by norms, understood as “standards of appropriate behaviour” (Finnemore and Sikkink 1998, 981) or “what good people do” (Fearon 1999, 27). What is considered “appropriate” or “good” is determined by the dominant group (i.e., in patriarchy, men). This hegemonic masculine order consequently creates a gendered social reality. Military masculinity (see Henry 2017, 187) extends this social order within the AF’s respective institutional body, such as the Bundeswehr. Epistemologically, this ontological standpoint justifies an interpretivist inquiry. This approach employs interpretivist methods that do not seek “objective” truths, but rather aim to make gendered power relations within the Bundeswehr visible, consistent with the feminist mandate to “draw attention” (see Sjoberg 2010, 602). For this purpose, Kanter’s (1977) concept of “Tokenism” from her seminal work, *Men and Women of the Corporation*, theorised that female underrepresentation (specifically, at shares below 15 %) structurally affects how women are viewed, the tasks they are assigned, and how their performance is judged (Kanter 1977, 383ff.):

- I. **High Visibility:** *They are constantly scrutinised.*
- II. **Contrast:** *They are seen primarily in opposition to the dominant group (men).*
- III. **Assimilation Pressure:** *They are pressured to adopt the norms of the dominant group.*

This dynamic creates a double standard: if a woman succeeds, this is often seen as a personal anomaly, sometimes attributed to her assimilation efforts. Conversely, if her performance is judged low, it is used to justify prejudice against the entire subgroup of women (see Kanter 1977, 385f.). This structural mechanism fits into Carreiras' *Women's Military Participation* framework (see Figure 1 below for a modified version), based on Segal's (1995, 759) earlier "Theory of Factors Affecting Women's Military Participation (WMP)".

Carreiras' conceptualised WMP as a product of overall gender relations trickling down into the AF, by both *external* (see Figure 1, in dashed lines) and *internal factors* (see AF in the box). By integrating Kanter's theory into the model as an internal factor within the AF, this study places the resulting category: **IV. Discursive Tokenism** as a key element affecting WMP, which, for the case study of this thesis, will be analysed through the Bundeswehr's social media content:

Figure 1: Placing Discursive Tokenism into Carreiras WMP Framework

Adapted from Carreiras' (2006, 19) *Women's Military Participation (WMP) Framework*. It has been simplified to focus on the Armed Forces (I, II, III) and modified to integrate Kanter's Tokenism Theory (IV. Discursive Tokenism) into the upcoming FVNA coding structure.

4.2. Data Collection, Sampling and Coding

For a full account of the procedure and methodological justifications, see **Appendix I**; the following section outlines the sourcing process concisely.

The social media content has been collected, based on criteria for source selection depicted in Table 2, ensuring replicability, transparency and purposefulness:

Table 2: Criteria for Source Selection

I. CRITERION	II. RULE OF INCLUSION	III. RATIONALE
1. TIMEFRAME: (2022–2025)	<i>Content needs to be published within the set timeframe (2022–2025).</i>	<i>Captures the Zeitenwende and Kriegstüchtigkeit discourses.</i>
2. PUBLISHER: (@BUNDESWEHR)	<i>Content needs to be published by official Bundeswehr channels/accounts</i>	<i>Ensures accountability of material sources. Avoids third-party material.</i>
3. ACCESSIBILITY: (ONLINE)	<i>Content needs to be publicly accessible on relevant platforms (without a user account)</i>	<i>Ensures unrestricted access to material and aligns with the requirements of the RQ and the FVNA methodology.</i>
4. MEDIUM (VISUAL)	<i>Content needs to contain a visual element</i>	<i>FVNA requirement. Selected Platforms focus on visuals.</i>
5. SUBJECT: (GENDER)	<i>Content needs to reveal gendered roles, discursively interpretable as “masculine” or “feminine”.</i>	<i>Ensures the discursive representation of gender (roles) for explanatory power.</i>
6. INTENTION: (FEMALE RECRUITMENT)	<i>Material needs to include imperative elements showing the intent of (Women’s) recruitment (such as links and means directing to the Bundeswehr’s recruitment websites/addresses, e.g.).</i>	<i>Aligning with the focus of the RQ. The channel “Bundeswehr-karriere” (career) explicitly signals this intent through its institutional framing.</i>

To improve the potential alignment between the sources and the RQ (i.e., Contextual Plausibility / Meaning-making), an initial two-step sampling was conducted: At first, relevant social media platforms for this thesis have been identified, based on audience demographics, requested formally from the Bundeswehr (see E-Mail confirmation dated November 11th 2025⁷), the findings of the German youth, information, media (*JIM*) study, and the outlined Criteria in Table 2 above. The identified platforms are: *Instagram*, *TikTok* and *YouTube* (see Appendix I for the extended rationale). A web-crawler tool called *Apify*⁸ was used to collect all necessary metadata (i.e. title, description, web address and further information) from the three chosen platforms, resulting in a raw dataset of $n=1179$ visual publications (see **Appendix II**).

⁷ **Note:** Due to confidentiality considerations, the e-mail correspondence is not included in the appendices.

⁸ **Note:** Documentation available under: <https://docs.apify.com/> (Last access: 6 January 2026).

The second step utilised keyword-based sampling (see Table 3) to tailor the $n=1179$ sources to fit the RQ better. The keywords have been assigned abductively, building on Kanter’s theoretical placement within the WMP framework (see Figure 1). It has been refined through preliminary testing with different terms, leading to the exclusion of initial keywords, such as *make-up, period, kids, or female fighter*⁹, as they did not yield any matches in the raw dataset:

Table 3: FVNA; Discursive Tokenism Keyword-based Filtering¹⁰

SET	CATEGORY	KEYWORDS
a)	Women’s role and function (I. Token: visibility)	<i>Soldatin, Soldat*in, Soldat/in; Rekrutin, Rekrut*in, Rekrut/in; Ärztin; Offizierin, Offizier*in, Offizier/in</i>
b)	Women’s identity and private life (II. Token: contrast)	<i>Frau, Frauen; Mutter; Familie</i>
c)	Gender ignorance/resistance (III. Token: Assimilation pressure)	<i>Diversity, Vielfalt; Gleichberechtigung; gender; ♀</i>

These Keywords aim to simulate a user’s active search for hashtags (#) (see Weimann and Masri 2020, 9f.) or textual descriptions to find user-specific content. However, visibility of content in reality is mainly determined by the platform’s algorithm (see Galeazzi et al. 2025) and content moderation (rules and guidelines) (see Gillespie 2022). As a result, if users rely only on the platform’s algorithm for recommendations but do not actively search, content might be less frequently seen. Gillespie (2022, 1) further highlights that content moderation can involve the removal of content, as exhibited by the Bundeswehr’s “Join the Team” (*Komm in die Mannschaft*¹¹) YouTube video. This keyword-based filtering has the advantage of being interchangeable across all three chosen platforms. A filtered sample of $n=212$ (see Appendix II) was selected according to the criteria in Table 2 and the Keywords in Table 3. The sample for the upcoming FVNA analysis consists of $n=56$ YouTube videos, $n=120$ Instagram posts and $n=36$ TikTok videos. The rules of inclusion (see Table 2) and the keyword-based filtering (see Table 3) were followed thoroughly to ensure replicability of the data collection.

⁹ **Note:** In German: *Schminke; Periode; Kinder; Kämpferin*

¹⁰ **Note:** Translation: *Soldatin* (Female Soldier), *Soldat*in/Soldat/in* (Gender-neutral/inclusive Soldier), *Rekrutin* (Female Recruit), *Ärztin* (Female Doctor), *Offizierin/Offizier*in/Offizier/in* (Female/Gender-inclusive Officer), *Frau/Frauen* (Woman/Women), *Mutter* (Mother), *Familie* (Family), *Vielfalt* (Diversity), *Gleichberechtigung* (Equality).

¹¹ Bundeswehr Exclusive: *Komm in Die Mannschaft*. (0:29).<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wXd5noeRyxs>. (Last access: 22.09.2025).

The content was coded in MAXQDA Analytics Pro 26.0.0, a qualitative data analysis software that enables coding of visual material. The coding process proceeded in two rounds to ensure analytical rigour. The initial coding was abductively grounded in Kanter’s Discursive Tokenism (DT) effects, leading to four principal DT codes: *I: High Visibility*; *II: Contrast*; *III: Assimilation Pressure* and *IV: Low Visibility*. Low Visibility was added as an analytically controlling code to capture instances where token visibility was absent or marginalised. Further codes have been added during the coding process to extend the identification of DT patterns. These resulted in a final set of 16 analytical codes, including a “No-code” marker to identify content requiring exclusion. As the FVNA method asks, “What is not shown in the image or video” (see Table 4), the No-code category revealed patterns of explanatory value (see chapter 5.1). Figure 2 provides a concise overview of the methodology of this thesis, and the next chapter will apply the Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis (FVNA) to the data and present the findings:

Figure 2: Sequential Overview from Data Collection, Sampling to the FVNA Analysis

The figure shows the complete process of the undertaken source gathering and analysis, as described briefly in this chapter (4 Research Design). For a more extensive description, please go to Appendix I. Source: Own representation, including the works from Kanter (1977), Carreiras (2006) and Berg (2025)

4.3. Ethics and Limitations

As this thesis researches externalised, institutional communication, there is minimal risk regarding personal data. However, focusing on controlled narratives leads to methodological trade-offs, such as the exclusion of decentralised, user-generated content. As audience reception remains beyond the scope of this thesis, interviews with military personnel and targeted audiences should be a subject for future research. The role of platform politics and algorithms must also be acknowledged, as they additionally affect content visibility through user experiences. Passive scrolling differs from active, keyword-based searches, as utilised in this thesis. Mimicking the nature of algorithms would make the sampling more dynamic; furthermore, the effects of user-advertised targeting are unknown in this case. Lastly, as this research operates within gender binaries, it potentially neglects the “in-betweenness” of more diverse experiences.

The following chapter details the Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis (FVNA) framework employed to decode the discursive tokenism visible in recruitment content.

4.4. Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis

Guided by the theoretical framework of Tokenism, this thesis employs an FVNA (see Berg 2025, 106f.). Rooted in the interpretivist tradition and the “visual turn” (Bleiker 2018, 1), this method focuses on how visual narratives (see Wibben 2011) construct and communicate gender relations within the Bundeswehr. The analytical process is abductive (see Wodak 2002, 14); it utilises Kanter’s concepts as an interpretative lens rather than for strict deductive testing (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow 2012, 15). This allows for a movement between theory, data and context, resulting in the following analytical pillars:

Table 4: FVNA Content Analysis (Berg 2025)

The image/video itself:	What/Who appears in the image or video? What gendered subjects are reproduced? What is not shown in the image or video?
Focalisation:	Internal- (point of view) versus External- (point of view) focalisation
Visualisation:	Who is the intended audience of the image or video?
Narrative:	Is the narrative on “successful” women soldiers’ inclusion told?

Note on Refinement: This framework was adapted from Berg (2025).

5. Mapping Absence and Presence - A FVNA Analysis of Discursive Tokenism in the Bundeswehr’s online recruitment material

5.1. Analysis of Emergent Patterns: Code Relations and Findings

The FVNA, together with the theory-driven Discursive Tokenism codes, yielded 16 analytical codes that have been applied across the $n=212$ cases. The emerging patterns and visible co-occurrences, without claiming statistical depth, serve to guide the FVNA interpretation task. The code relations matrix, as discussed first, represents the interplay of specific codes, shedding light on three distinct discursive strategies manifest in the Bundeswehr’s online recruitment materials. These three strategies later structure the analysis.

Figure 3: MAXQDA Code Relations of $n=212$ cases

Note: ■ indicates more frequent overlaps of codes. “No-Code” (0.) was intentionally excluded from the mapping. The horizontal shaded bar maps the connections to Discursive Tokenism (DT I-IV), while the vertical bar underscores the centrality of “Military Masculine Norms” (Code 7).

Following the FSS scholarship, which seeks to uncover gendered effects that structure hegemonic masculinities, it was anticipated that **Code 7**: “Military Masculine Norms,” would co-occur with nearly all other identified codes. The notable exceptions of this pattern are **Code 12**: “Private / Family Life” and **Code 13**: “Geopolitical Situation” — likely because these themes are addressed less frequently ($n=19$ and $n=5$, respectively). Additionally, it suggests that the “Private / Family Life” content, if present, does not strongly align with masculine themes, as indicated by its more feminine-coded nature (see Table 1: “Key Terms”). The ties between masculinity and Code 2.2: “External Focalisation”, reveal another notable strategy. Strategy here refers to the intentional use of visualities and content to produce and reproduce a particular narrative. External focalisation refers to a more distanced point of view through camera positioning (see Table 4). External focalisation was predominantly used when showcasing military equipment, such as naval vessels, from a distance. This was often accompanied by “dramatic” musical underscoring.

Dramatic, i.e. war-themed music is interpreted to empower (see Koelsch et al. 2019) audiences upholding masculine ideals (i.e. men) (see Haq and Rashid 2018, 112). Audience demographics support this insight, particularly on platforms like YouTube and Instagram (77.6 % male), with an average age range¹² of 25 to 34 years (48.1 % and 44.2 %). A nuanced gender distribution¹³ is observed only on TikTok, where women's share is at 46 %. TikTok also has the youngest audience, predominantly 18-25 and 25-34 (48.9 % and 48.2 %, respectively). This audience distribution possibly affects the more frequent use of Code 2.1: “Internal Focalisation”, alongside Code 6: “Women as Soldier Integration”, showing more personalised successful integration narratives.

There was minimal overlap between **Code 7**: “Military Masculine Norms” and **Code 5**: “Narrative of [women soldiers] Successful Integration”, which primarily connects with Code 1: “Discursive Tokenism I: High Visibility”. This observed co-occurrence is not coincidental but appears to be part of a gender mainstreaming strategy, which will be examined in greater detail in *Chapter 5.2: The Strategy of Hypervisibility*.

Building on the unexpected connection between Code 10: “Physical Requirements” (i.e., strength) and Code 11: “Non-Physical Requirements” (i.e. static balance), *Chapter 5.3: The Strategy of Conditional Belonging*, will discuss the conditional tension found in DT II: “Assimilation Pressures” and gendered DT III: “Contrast-” making.

Absence was found to be a “hidden” hegemonic power, centred on the reproduction of Code 7 military masculinity norms. Gender silencing oscillates ambiguously, functioning as a structuring element, as *Chapter 5.4: The Power of Absence* will discuss.

Chapters 5.2 to 5.4 consequently analyse three interrelated modes through which gender is negotiated in the Bundeswehr’s digital recruitment material. Read sequentially, these chapters demonstrate how visibility, conditional inclusion, and exclusion operate as complementary discursive strategies rather than isolated phenomena. The thesis concludes with Chapters 6.1 and 6.2, which summarise the findings and outline avenues for future research.

¹² **Note:** Not differentiated by gender / sex.

¹³ **Note:** The data is derived from a German source, resulting in ambiguity between the terms “gender” and “sex.” I interpreted the given data in a gendered sense as making a difference between men and women and diverse individuals.

5.2. The strategy of Hypervisibility (DT I)

The strategic placement of women soldiers — effectively reproducing the Bundeswehr's narrative of “successful integration” — was found 55 times in the analysed material. The code was placed whenever a woman soldier was overly made visible, which mostly appeared during close-up interviews (see Figure 4). “High Visibility” content frequently employs Code 2.1: “Internal Focalisation”, which captures the reduction in distance between the subject and the viewer. This immersive approach conveys narratives by fostering intimacy with the audience (see Genette 1980). In this vein, one emergent pattern was the reframing of **Code 8**: “Challenging Masculine Norms” Attempting to transform the hegemonic masculine ideal of Code 7 into a personal challenge a woman soldier must overcome. This shift moves attention away from structural or institutional exclusion toward individual success narratives. Women soldiers are depicted as proving themselves within the hegemonic masculine setting of the AF, thereby reproducing the masculine norms associated with Code 7.

For instance, one officer — a *Flottillenärztin*,¹⁴ recounts that her career was motivated by the belief that “what men are doing, I can also do; I liked the challenge” (@Bundeswehrkarriere 2025a, 00:12 – 00:20). Her role as a medical doctor was a profession open to women prior to the landmark *Kreil vs. Bundesregierung* judgment in 2001 (see *Tanja Kreil v Bundesrepublik Deutschland* 2000). Today, this is reflected in the fact that women account for approximately 45% of personnel in medical functions across all branches of the armed forces (BMVg 2019, 21). Furthermore, of the three women generals in the Bundeswehr — the highest rank possible — two have a background in medicine (Bundeswehr 2025a).

In contrast, another navy officer — a *Kapitänleutnant*,¹⁵ recalls her career as a radar operator (@Bundeswehrkarriere 2025a, 01:00-02:00). Her career path was made possible only by the *Kreil* judgment, underscoring the practical significance of this landmark case.

While the women soldiers depicted suggest a somewhat tokenistic framing, they nevertheless convey a convincing narrative of successful integration by emphasising their ability to perform military duties effectively. Rather than portraying themselves as “victims” of hegemonic masculinity, they adopt an emancipatory stance, claiming that the Bundeswehr is a supportive yet challenging environment for individual growth (@Bundeswehrkarriere 2025a, 00:00 – 03:00; 2025b; @Bundeswehrexclusive 2023a, 00:00 – 01:28).

¹⁴ **Note:** Flotille doctor: NATO OF - 4

¹⁵ **Note:** Lieutenant Commander: NATO OF - 3

However, it must be noted cautiously that official Bundeswehr accounts publish these videos with a clear strategic recruitment intent (see panels a–d). Consequently, the material is curated to effectively show elements that confirm the official narrative of “successful integration.” Nevertheless, these challenges are consistent with Kanter’s (1977) observation regarding the twofold effects of high visibility for women soldiers. While it remains likely that a woman soldier’s mistake (e.g., during training) could be used to reinforce gender prejudices (Bundestag 2025c, 12), this cannot be confirmed by the analysed material. This is partly because of its curated, strategic recruitment intent (BMVg 2019, 15–19).

On the other hand, the frequent connection to the emancipatory Code 8: “Challenging Masculine Norms,” does suggest a more positive meaning behind the content analysed. Put into perspective, the Bundeswehr in 2019 produced high-visibility content with an emancipatory aim (see BMVg 2019): “*Die Rekrutinnen*¹⁶” (@Bundeswehrexclusive 2019) — resulting in a significantly more problematic portrayal of women soldiers than the material analysed here. The emphasis on achieving an emancipatory and successful status within a masculine domain was, for instance, captured by connecting athletics with the military profession in panels a) and c) of Figure 4 below:

Figure 4: Exemplary recruitment content for Discursive Tokenism I (High Visibility)

Note: Composite figure developed by the author.¹⁷
a): (@Bundeswehrkarriere 2025b; TikTok);
b): (@Bundeswehrkarriere 2024a; TikTok);
c): (@Bundeswehrkarriere 2024c; Instagram);
d): (@Bundeswehrexclusive 2023a; YouTube).

¹⁶ **Note:** Translates to: “The female recruits”

¹⁷ **Note:** Unless stated otherwise, all figures are developed by the author. All panels consist of screenshots from official Bundeswehr social media recruitment materials.

Panel **a**) presents Cora, a sports soldier stating: “When people say a woman doesn’t belong in football, I can only shake my head, because I think you shouldn’t judge until you’ve seen it for yourself” (Figure 4, panel a¹⁸, 00:30-00:40). Cora is joined by another women soldier called Laura in the rank of being a Corporal¹⁹, wearing camouflage, visually reinforcing the double meaning of Cora’s statement. Laura adds: “I learned to stick to what I want to achieve in the Bundeswehr” (ibid., 00:50 – 00:55).

Both sequences convey the empowering message of individual success despite structural resistance, leaving unaddressed the origins of such. Cora then concludes the segment by framing the clip’s recruitment rationale: “We are a little bit of an inspiration for all the girls and women out there” (ibid., 00:55 – 01:03). This statement frames the highly visible women soldiers not merely as service members in military functions, but as role-models actively encouraging female participation in traditionally male-dominated fields — both sports and the military. This nexus between the military profession and sports was prevalent across much of the analysed material; for instance, the soldier featured in panel **(c)** is depicted as an avid runner shown in slow motion preceding her interview (see Figure 4, panel c).

As Herbert (1998, 7f.) noted, there is a historical parallel between women joining the military and women doing sports. Both were traditionally seen as activities “real women” would not perform, as this could “cause damage to the reproductive system” (ibid.). A recent medical study by L’Heveder et al. (2026) shows that while *elite athletes* may indeed experience “menstrual disturbances” (ibid.,13), physical activity, to the contrary, is associated with health benefits, including improved fertility up to a certain threshold (ibid., 5). In contrast to recruitment narratives that suggest physical egalitarianism — promoting fitness activities for both genders equally — the Bundeswehr explicitly notes that, in the basic fitness test, “genetically caused age or sex differences will be weighted in” (own translation, Bundeswehr 2025b, 2).

This tension between not mentioning differentiated evaluations in athletic recruitment content while applying them in practice illustrates a central dilemma of the Bundeswehr’s gender mainstreaming strategy. While recruitment narratives emphasise de-gendering through uniformity and socialisation, gender difference continues to be institutionally recognised and operationalised.

¹⁸ **Note:** Visual and audiovisual material is cited via figure and panel references in the text, with full source information provided in the figure captions and reference list.

¹⁹ **Note:** *Stabsgefreite*: NATO-OR4.

Following Butler's concept of gender performativity, "doing gender" is understood here as the repeated enactment of gendered norms that make difference intelligible rather than neutralising it (Butler 1999, 41). As long as gender difference remains institutionally salient, such performances risk reinforcing gendered prejudices and enabling tokenistic evaluations of women soldiers (see Kümmel 2008; 2014b; 2015).

The principle of gender mainstreaming — defined here as mandatory gender-sensitising practices and gender training — is formally integrated into the Bundeswehr's institutional guidelines (BMVg 2019). It is embedded within the broader doctrine of "inner leadership,"²⁰ which constitutes a core normative framework of the Bundeswehr (Gady 2026, 167). This doctrine is institutionalised through the *Zentrum Innere Führung*²¹ (ZIF), established in 1956 to link the ethical ideal of the "citizen in uniform" to the constitutional foundations of the post-war German state (Gady 2026, 167ff.), making the Bundeswehr a *sui generis* given its historical roots.

This institutional commitment becomes visible, for instance, in panel (d), which depicts Oberleutnant Jessica commanding an artillery battery. Beyond interview sequences, she is shown issuing orders to men soldiers, exemplifying visual narratives of women's integration into the military *par excellence* (see Code 6). While the concept of gender mainstreaming, therefore, is part of the Innere Führung concept – seeking to improve what is guaranteed by the constitution: "the equality between men and women"²² (GG Article 3, (2)), the low number of women soldiers contrasts with the positive framing of successful integration of women soldiers.

As argued in the Introduction, the soldiers' law of equality, the state and its organisations fail to meet their legal requirements. This remains untouched by the predominant positive portrayal of women. While the Bundeswehr employs this logic as a strategic manoeuvre to advance a narrative of "successful integration," it simultaneously attempts to make women soldiers of their forces visible by empowering them, as in the case of Cora. She stated rightfully that women like her are placed as highly visible "role models" for the intended audience.

²⁰ **Note:** "Innere Führung"

²¹ **Note:** ZIF translates to "Centre for Inner Leadership"

²² Grundgesetz (Basic Law), Article 3(2), own translation: "Men and women shall have equal rights. The state shall promote the actual implementation of equal rights for women and men and shall take steps to eliminate existing disadvantages."

Discursive Tokenism I, when emergent, was therefore confirming but also challenging Kanter's (1977) concept, as captured in another individualised story by *Hauptfeldwebel*²³ Anita featured in panel **b**), who asserts:

Being a woman in the Bundeswehr? – I will tell you why this works for me [...] being a woman and being in the Bundeswehr does match for me, because the sex/gender does not play any role. What matters is skills, fitness and performance [...] as a woman, you can follow all career paths in the Bundeswehr. (Figure 4, panel b; @Bundeswehrkarriere 2024a, 00:00-00:28).

While this quotation could also be situated in the subsequent chapter — given its reference to physical fitness and performance — it is analytically anchored here because it exemplifies a conditional logic of inclusion. The narrative constructs gender neutrality as an ideal, yet simultaneously implies a set of conditions women must fulfil, amounting to a form of gender-neutral assimilation pressure. This representation, therefore, warrants critical scrutiny. The claim that gender “does not play any role,” alongside the emphasis on “skills, fitness and performance,” raises the question of whether career paths in the Bundeswehr are genuinely detached from gender, or whether masculine-coded standards (see Code 7) are simply rendered invisible through a discourse of gender neutrality.

5.3. The Strategy of “Conditional Belonging” (DT II & III)

Conditional belonging is understood as a discursive logic that oscillates between demands for “Assimilation Pressure” (DT II) and the simultaneous marking of gendered difference through “Contrast” (DT III). This section examines how this tension is negotiated through comradeship, physical capability, and performance. In extension of the gender-mainstreaming strategy discussed in the previous section for High Visibility (DT I), conditional belonging is constantly articulated through a “gender-neutral” soldier identity, conflicting with the images analysed. The camouflaged uniform symbolises this logic. It distinguishes civilians from military personnel and is also intended to marginalise gender differences through a narrative in which “gender does not play any role because performance does,” as discussed in the previous section (see Figure 4, panel b).

However, as current reports indicate, lived experiences of comradeship within the AF are rarely grounded in a genuinely gender-neutral understanding (Bundestag 2025c, 120ff.). Instead, comradeship is often structured along gendered lines, shaped by assumptions about male and female bodies and their respective capabilities (Bundestag 2025c, 84; 95–99). This introduces a conditional layer of belonging, whereby not all women, but only those who conform to

²³ **Note:** Sergeant Major: NATO: OR-7 / OR-8

prevailing masculine norms, are recognised as “comrades” through successful assimilation (see Kümmel 2014, 7–14). As stated in the introduction, a notable connection is evident between **Code 10**, Physical Requirements (i.e., strength-based fitness), and the broader capability demands captured in **Code 11** (e.g., static balance, flexibility, and cognitive agility). As Carreiras (2006, 90) argues, military fitness standards are often biased towards raw strength, thereby overlooking bodily competencies such as flexibility, where women may hold a physiological advantage. This is supported by Allison et al. (2015, 18), who find that while men outperform women in anaerobic power, women soldiers demonstrate superior static balance.

While such assessments are officially presented as equally fair for men and women, the Bundeswehr simultaneously emphasises women’s operational capability by noting that women “fly combat aircraft and helicopters [...] and command naval ships” (Bundeswehr 2025a). However, none of the analysed recruitment material visually depicts women in these roles, revealing a disjunction between institutional claims of capability and their visual representation. Rather than maintaining a hierarchical model that privileges anaerobic power and masculine norms above all else, the literature (see, for instance, Alison 2004; Carreiras 2006; Knapik et al. 2009; Allison et al. 2015; Nindl et al. 2016; 2017; RAND 2024) suggests that role-based, gender-neutral capability assessments could optimise operational effectiveness by aligning specific bodily strengths with specific mission requirements.

For specific roles such as becoming a fighter pilot, this might be, to some degree, connected to the rigorous testing of applicants, where only 3 % (e.g., 21 of 680 in 2017) succeeded in the initial screening (Bundesregierung 2019). This rigorous selection could be interpreted by some men — though not by the scholars themselves — as evidence that men are inherently better conditioned, cognitively and physically, than women to perform as pilots; such interpretations reflect broader gendered perceptions rather than empirical evidence (see Kümmel 2015 on gender stereotypes in the Bundeswehr). The appeal of becoming a fighter pilot in extension may be stronger for men than for women due to its persistent masculine imagery, heavily reinforced by popular culture (e.g., films like *Top Gun*; Wilder 2017). As reported by former fighter pilot Major²⁴ Nicola Winter (Winter in Focus.de 2024), only three women flew combat aircraft in the Bundeswehr at all (ibid.). Winter, who is a reserve pilot for the European Space Agency, would, in this strain of interpretation, be seen as an exception (i.e., a woman in the cockpit²⁵). While Winter could become even a reserve astronaut, most women would be

²⁴ **Note:** Major: NATO OF-3

²⁵ **Note:** The term “cockpit” originates from the violent, male-centric practice of cockfighting (Oxford Dictionary:

incapable of doing so. This shows the twofold nature of Kanter's DT with respect to visibility. Women's success in a "men's world" becomes individualised, while their failure becomes collectively instrumentalised. This elitist character of roles also applies to the *Kommando Spezialkräfte* (KSK; special forces), where no women have ever served, and only four have applied in more than 25 years (Bundeswehr 2021). The Bundeswehr emphasises that the physical requirements are used as a gatekeeper to maintain the "quality of the special services" – regardless of gender (ibid.). Nevertheless, the absence of women soldiers in these roles suggests the existence of role-bound biological differences between females and males, which is framed as almost impossible to overcome for women, therefore justifying the exclusion. It remains somewhat unclear if this is true for the presented roles. Especially when following Carreiras' argument of male bias in the testing of applicants (Carreiras 2006, 91).

Consequently, even if current testing procedures are based on medical standards, these standards remain predominantly oriented towards male bodies (see, for instance, Hamberg 2008; Brown et al. 2020; Tsukahara et al. 2022), reflecting a broader hegemonic masculine structure that continues to shape the Bundeswehr's assessment of applicants. The KSK's use of women for missions like "searching Muslim women in culturally sensible environments²⁶" (Bundeswehr 2021) demonstrates that the military recognises the unique operational value of women's skills and gender only when it is tactically advantageous. This directly challenges the narrative that functional (i.e., physical) barriers alone prevent women from being included in KSK operations, suggesting that prejudice or institutional reluctance may be another gatekeeper for women to participate in special forces operations fully. This does not negate that certain roles have specific physical requirements and standards that are also unattainable for most men. As this thesis is not aimed at assessing operational standards or the special forces' role selection, but at merely representing and interpreting underrepresentation through a feminist lens, this is beyond the scope of advanced analysis. Nevertheless, as Wibben (2016a) notes regarding the narrative use of U.S. "Female Engagement Teams" (FETs) during Operation Enduring Freedom (2001–2014) in Afghanistan, the KSK's approach implies that cultural barriers can be overcome simply by deploying a woman to engage with another woman. This narrative, however, neglects a myriad of complex political and social factors, thus presenting a picture of false emancipation (or instrumentally presented equality), given the true, low overall representation of women in

<https://web.archive.org/web/20120801042626/http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/cockpit>).

Its continued use in military aviation acts as linguistic reinforcement for the masculine visual default.

²⁶ Note: "Muslim women" are most likely used as an example due to the Bundeswehr's engagement in Afghanistan and given the social impropriety that men would search a woman in certain Muslim contexts.

the Bundeswehr, and in the KSK in particular. The Bundeswehr's representation strategy demonstrates an apparent tension between different modes of inclusion. While the low quantitative representation of women in elite roles made achieving "simple presence" (basic visual inclusion) difficult, the Bundeswehr historically sought to present women to its audience as experts in their profession (BMVg 2019, 89), thereby signalling a qualified presence approach. However, the striking finding of this analysis is the subsequent decline: as Chapter 5.4, *The Power of Absence*, will show, the 2022–2025 content corpus sometimes failed to present a woman at all. This lack of visual representation, even if it were rectified with new imagery, would still face the challenge of "meaningful integration," potentially equating to Zalewski's notion of "add[ing] women and stir" (Zalewski 1993, 15). This critical tension highlights the difference between what Carreiras (2006, 98) termed *simple presence* versus *qualified presence*. Qualified presence is necessary to prevent fundamental differences regarding women's roles from remaining invisible. The Bundeswehr's older content featuring Major Winter, while beyond the scope of this analysis, serves as a "best practice" for qualified presence, normalising women in highly advanced combat roles (Bundeswehr 2017). The fact that this *best practice* is not mirrored in the recent content analysed reveals a much more nuanced, and often problematic, picture of women's representation in terms of mere simple presence. This is noteworthy, as it confounds the opposing character of DT I High Visibility, which was more often positively connoted due to the empowering messaging. Contrasting material was found $n=32$ times, also in patternful combination with DT IV high-visible content, for instance, when hairstyles or makeup appropriate for women were discussed. In some content, the opposite occurred when a higher-ranked man gave orders or judged lower-ranked women soldiers (i.e., recruits). While this thesis must exclude the structural dimensions of women's participation, as depicted in Carreiras' WMP framework (Carreiras 2006, 19; see Figure 1), structural effects are becoming visible in the material analysed.

Taken together, the findings in this section demonstrate how the Bundeswehr's recruitment discourse constructs women's belonging as conditional: women are included only insofar as they assimilate to masculine performance norms (DT III), while their gendered difference is simultaneously marked through contrast (DT II). Rather than resolving this tension, recent recruitment content oscillates between overburdening women with symbolic representational work and rendering them visually absent altogether. This dynamic reproduces the core logic of DT, shifting from conditional inclusion to non-representation — a pattern that becomes more pronounced in the analysis of low visibility and absence in the following section.

5.4. The Power of Absence (No-Code and DT IV)

Initially, this content was supposed to be excluded from the analysis for two reasons. At first, given the keyword-based sample developed, no pattern was anticipated. Secondly, the number of “No-Codes” was expected to be lower. This means that there was a mismatch between the post/video descriptions and the content shown. For instance, the keyword “*Soldatin*” (women soldier) (see Table 3) was used generically also for content unrelated to women soldiers, showing, for example, warships and their male crew-members (see following Figure 5). The recurring patterns of masculinity found were evident and proved too crucial to ignore. This methodological shift provides clear evidence for the concept of gendered silencing in making maleness (i.e., masculinity) the unquestioned norm (see Criado-Perez 2020, 23) by revealing the default visual language of the Bundeswehr’s recruitment channels when women are absent. This section, therefore, is dedicated to contextualising the further DT (I – IV) findings of the primary FVNA, as can be seen exemplarily in Figure 5 below. The exemplified Instagram video is showing an advertisement titled: “Dive into our world” for the *Marine* (Navy). The content utilises dramatic music, fast-paced action cuts from people (internal focalisation) to the frigate “Rheinland Pfalz” (external focalisation), and scenes of soldiers in full gear (e.g., jumping into a Rigid Inflatable Boat), which is specifically designed to look appealing to an audience interested in heroism, action, and physical prowess, which is most likely men.

Figure 5: Exemplary “No-code” Recruitment Sequence

Note: Composite figure developed by the author. Panels a) through d) represent the chronological flow of a single video post/story sequence, exemplifying a “no-code” narrative structure in which military hardware, elite male soldiers, and abstract branding substitute for explicit inclusion or representation of women soldiers.
Source: (@Bundeswehrkarriere 2024b, 00:00-00:21; Instagram and TikTok)

The reliance on such “strong music” and “strong images” is not surprising, yet it is a confirming, almost cliché feature of militarised media culture (see Der Derian 2009). Similar patterns have been found $n=30$ times in excluded “No-code” content; intentional, strategic use of such imagery can be assumed. Koelsch et al. (2019, 1) show that “heroic music evoked more positive, exciting, constructive, and motivating thoughts” in participants (i.e. the targeted audience). This combination of images and underlying music, therefore, again establishes a gendered visual default through the sheer volume of its repetition. This gendered silencing denies the possibility of women soldiers’ qualified presence (Carreiras 2006, 98).

The masculine imagery and masculine music visually reinforce a traditional “man’s world” archetype, creating a striking contrast with the Bundeswehr’s initial quote, asserting that women “command naval ships.” While certainly women do serve in this domain (1,749 women soldiers, equating to 11.43 % of the *Marines*’ total force) (Bundeswehr 2025a), their complete exclusion from these high-production recruitment clips highlights their systematic exclusion.

The masculine-material focus in *No-code* material is also evident in panels a) and c):

Figure 6: Gendered “No-code” Content in Bundeswehr Recruitment Campaigns

a)

b)

c)

Note: All three panels exemplify “no-code” recruitment content by foregrounding male-coded military hardware or abstracted male figures, while excluding women soldier narratives of inclusion.

Source: (@Bundeswehreclusive 2024; Instagram):

a) Translation: “Do what matters - Full Commitment for the Peace – Because you can”

b) Translation: “Do what matters - Flying with Mach 2 for Freedom – Because you can”

c) Translation: “Do what matters - You keep 7000 t on course – Because you can”

While for such content no “heroic music” was played, the imagery —in a more abstract way — focuses heavily on military equipment, as seen in the Eurofighter picture on the right (“Flying with Mach 2 for Freedom – Because you can”), or the right graphic: “You keep 7000t on course – Because you can.” The interpretation that the “you” refers to masculine men, given the findings, does not seem to be too far-fetched. The campaign’s abstract emphasis on flying for “Freedom” (see Figure 6), particularly in the call to “fly with Mach 2 for freedom,” suggests the focus on the experiential freedom of the pilot — the thrill and autonomy of high-speed flight — rather than the abstract, constitutional freedom guaranteed to the nation.

The post in the middle was excluded, as it depicts a man in a field medical role standing in front of an Armoured Personnel Carrier. In this context, the red cross as a symbol of lifesaving, combined with the slogan “Full commitment for peace,” reproduces a masculine trope of the soldier as a professional lifesaver. This figure is framed as competent and self-sacrificing (“-because you can”), positioned as fighting for the peace of others and potentially risking or giving his life in the process. The dramatic staging of the soldier and material reminds one of the sequence depicted in Figure 5. The fact that other imagery in the same campaign (same post) does feature women does not negate the pattern of silencing presented; it merely illustrates that the Bundeswehr is maintaining the masculine visual default, employing women mostly in tokenistic depictions.

By contextualising these figures, the observation that this content might be produced mainly for men can be confirmed by the Bundeswehr's audience demographics (Bundeswehr E-Mail confirmation from 11. November 2025): On Instagram — the source of the graphics — the audience demographics consists of 77,6 % male persons, of which 44,2 % (the majority) is between 25-34 years old. While this is true for the whole account @Bundeswehrkarriere, limiting the analysis of single posts and their audience demographics, there might be content that, in isolation, could be more appealing to women than to men. As the audience's reaction was excluded from this thesis, no statement will be made about it, as this would require a different methodological approach and could lead to future research on the reception of selected content. As can be argued, the similarity in function between No-Code content and DT IV: Low Visibility is further contributing to the difference-making of women soldiers, as the previous chapter has discussed under the DT II and DT III (Contrast and Assimilation Pressures). The functioning of a gendered silencer can be seen in the content of Figure 7, below.

Figure 7: Women Soldiers in Short Cut Sequences

Composed Sources:

- a.) (@Bundeswehrexclusive 2025a; Instagram)
- b.) (@Bundeswehrexclusive 2025c; Instagram)
- c.) (@Bundeswehrexclusive 2025b; Instagram)
- d.) (@Bundeswehrexclusive 2023b; YouTube)

The overlap can be explained by the co-occurrence with the seventh contextual code. In other words, **Code 7**: “Military Masculinity” follows the same logic as in the “**No-code**” category.

When masculine, military men predominantly appear, women are hard to find. Nevertheless, on the other hand, some women, despite their short sequence, appeared to be in functionally important or warrior-like functions (see panels a-d). Further, in some sequences, women were shown as training officers commanding male and female recruits. In short, the argument of this thesis is supported by the partial visibility of women.

Low institutional representation is thus visually reproduced through selective and abbreviated portrayals, reinforcing masculine military norms (see Code 7) rather than challenging them. While the effects of such representation on recruitment outcomes cannot be assessed within the scope of this thesis, the material analysed strongly suggests — consistent with FSS scholarship — that the persistence of gendered silencing and partial visibility is likely to contribute to the continued low engagement of women in the armed forces.

6. Conclusion

6.1. Findings

This thesis asked: *To what extent do Bundeswehr social media campaigns (2022–2025) targeting women reproduce or challenge gendered framings of women’s soldiership?*

The analysis demonstrates that the Bundeswehr’s digital recruitment material operates through three dominant and interrelated discursive strategies: *hypervisibility*, *conditional belonging*, and *gendered absence/silencing*. Across the n=212 analysed cases, *Military Masculine Norms* (Code 7) emerged as the central organising principle structuring both the presence and absence of women soldiers. Visual strategies such as external focalisation, dramatic music, and equipment-centred imagery predominantly reproduce masculine-coded narratives of military professionalism and heroism. The (in)visibility of women soldiers is therefore not random, but strategically produced.

The strategy of hypervisibility constructs women soldiers as individually successful role models, shifting attention away from organisational and structural factors that continue to hinder women’s integration. “Successful integration” is framed as a personal achievement rather than an institutional responsibility. While gender neutrality is presented as an ideal, it implicitly requires women to perform masculine-coded standards of fitness, resilience, and professionalism. Hypervisibility thus operates ambivalently: it symbolically empowers women while simultaneously burdening them with representational labour, confirming Kanter’s (1977) observations on the double-edged nature of visibility. Even when women appear in highly qualified roles, they are frequently positioned as symbolic representatives of gender equality rather than as normalised military professionals.

This thesis demonstrates that questions of gender equality and recruitment cannot be treated as peripheral or merely symbolic concerns. The findings indicate that women’s integration is visually and discursively isolated from broader narratives of operational readiness, despite empirical evidence from Feminist Security Studies linking gender diversity to military effectiveness. Recruitment communication itself may thus contribute to sustaining gendered exclusion at a time when personnel shortages and legitimacy pressures are intensifying. Addressing these representational dynamics is therefore not only normatively relevant but also strategically significant.

6.2. Contribution and Future Research

This thesis contributes to the research programme of Feminist Security Studies, situated within War Studies, by demonstrating the analytical value of Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis. Examining visual recruitment narratives highlights the presence and effects of Discursive Tokenism and its implications for military recruitment, with relevance beyond the German case. While this study focuses on the production of visual narratives, future research should incorporate audience-centred approaches. Building on these findings, subsequent studies could examine how discursive tokenism shapes recruitment outcomes by analysing how different gendered audiences interpret recruitment imagery, for example, through interviews with recruits or reception-based studies. Such research would allow for a more comprehensive assessment of how visual strategies influence identification, motivation, and perceptions of belonging within the armed forces. In times of AI-generated content and algorithmic content selection, a closer examination of how technology shapes user-experienced perception appears increasingly unavoidable.

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Primary Analysed Corpus: Cited Materials (n = 212)

Materials systematically analysed using Feminist Visual Narrative Analysis and used within the thesis. The full dataset is archived in the OSF repository (see Appendix II).

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Appendix I: Detailed Content Sampling and Codebook

Content Sampling: Step-by-Step Procedures

A three-step sequencing approach was conducted, as follows:

Step 1: In the first sequencing round, the targets to source from were defined based on the RQ focus on digital recruitment material and potential female recruits' media consumption (i.e. targeted audience). According to the *Jugend, Information, Medien (JIM Study*²⁷) (Youth Information Media Study) (12–19 years, $n=1,200$) the three most relevant social media platforms for young women are: Instagram (66% women share), TikTok (63% women share) and YouTube, included also for its indispensable role in long-form video, given its high adolescent usage (80% of the age group are spending 91 minutes daily) (mpfs 2023, 40). These platforms further fit the basic definition of what accounts as a “Social Media platform”, defined as an online, digital service containing user-generated content to communicate to a virtual community (see Leonardi, Huysman, and Steinfield 2013, 2; Obar and Wildman 2015). Yet the number of followers indicates a high audience flow:

- **Instagram:** @Bundeswehrkarriere = 198.000 follower
- **TikTok:** @Bundeswehrkarriere = 432.200 follower
- **YouTube:** @Bundeswehrexclusive = 529.000 follower²⁸

To gain further insight into the targeted audience and to compare it with the real demographics (gender and age shares), a formal request was submitted to the Bundeswehr's media officers. Although the data contained sensitive, summarised information, the Bundeswehr agreed to share the requested data for the exclusive purpose of this thesis (**E-mail confirmation dated November 11, 2025**), confirming the relevance of the chosen social media platforms.

Data collection: A web-crawler tool called *Apify*²⁹ was used to collect all necessary metadata from the three chosen platforms (@Bundeswehrkarriere on Instagram and TikTok, and @Bundeswehrexclusive³⁰ on YouTube between October 2022 – 2025, via Apify's preprogrammed script. Data collection was restricted to the 2022 – 2025 period, as this timeframe captures the *Zeitenwende* (change of times) discourse and the security policy shift following the invasion of Ukraine (see Blumenau 2022; Fröhlich 2023), which significantly increased the public and strategic visibility of Bundeswehr recruitment efforts (see Die Zeit

²⁷ **Note:** The *Jugend, Information, Medien (JIM)* study (Youth, Information, Media study) is a yearly conducted study, published since 1998 by the *Medienpädagogische Forschungsverband Südwest* (mpfs): <https://mpfs.de/>.

²⁸ **Note:** Last access: 18.11.2025

²⁹ **Note:** See more on Apify's documentation <https://docs.apify.com/>

2025; Politico 2025; Mais 2025). The raw data collection took place on the 16th of October 2025. The TikTok-scraper found $n=541$, the Instagram-scraper $n= 542$ and the YouTube-scraper $n=96$ entries. The lower volume of content on YouTube reflects its purpose of being a platform for longer video content. The raw dataset consists of $n=1179$ visual publications.

Step 2: For the second sequencing round, a keyword-based approach (see Tables 3 and 7) was employed to filter the raw material for greater relevance to the research questions. Building upon the adapted WMP framework, keywords for this second sequencing were chosen based on the identified internal factors of WMP (see Figure 1). This systematic filtering method has the advantage of being used interchangeably across all three chosen platforms: TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube. As previously stated, the results of this systematic sampling are nevertheless not treated as a statistical finding that allows for objective, causal, or generalised claims.

Table 5: Keyword-Based Sampling Results

#Filter / set a);b);c)	English Translation	YouTube	Instagram	TikTok
a) Women´s role and function:				
#Soldatin	Female Soldier	84	137	15
#Soldati*in	*	0	1	1
#Soldat/in	*	0	6	2
#Rekrutin	Female Recruit	5	39	0
#Rekrut*in	*	0	0	0
#Rekruti/in	*	0	1	0
#Ärztin	Female Doctor	4	1	0
#Offizierin	Female Officer	10	10	9
#Offizier*in	*	0	0	0
#Offizier/in	*	0	2	0
b) Women´s identity and private life:				
#Frau	Woman	1	11	5
#Frauen	Women	0	8	5
#Mutter	Mother	0	5	0
#Familie	Family	1	9	0
c) Gender ignorance / resistance:				
#Diversity	*	0	3	0
#Vielfalt	Diversity	0	5	0
#Gleichberechtigung	Equality	0	0	0
#gender	*	0	2	0
#♀	*	1	12	6
Amount of Keywords found in sources: Σ		106	252	43

Step 3: A filtered sample of $n=212$ (see Appendix II) resulted following the criteria of Tables 2 and 3. The sample for the FVNA consists of $n=56$ YouTube videos, $n=120$ Instagram (video) posts and $n=36$ TikTok videos. While the number of TikTok videos in the sample is lower, noteworthy given its relevancy due to the average playtime of 568.505³¹ times. The rules of inclusion (see Table 2) and the keyword-based filtering (see Table 3) were followed strictly to ensure replicability of the data acquisition. This disproportionality is seen as acceptable due to the limitation of not making statistical inferred claims, the overlap of content on Instagram and TikTok (same username and administration) and the potential bias in manually selecting content, which would undermine the purpose of the approaches outlined in Tables 2 and 3.

MAXQDA: The final sample was then downloaded to be analysed. For this purpose, the content was imported into MAXQDA³² (Analytics Pro 26.0.0), a leading Qualitative Data Analysis (QDA) software, allowing to transcribe and coding of Visual Narratives and Discursive Tokenism.

Two-Step Coding Process for the FVNA Analysis; Abductive Grounding: The coding process proceeded in two distinct rounds to ensure analytical rigour. The initial coding was abductively grounded in Kanter's Discursive Tokenism (DT) effects, which informed the development of four initial primary DT codes: I: High Visibility; II: Contrast; III: Assimilation Pressure and IV: Low Visibility. Additional codes have been added during the coding to identify possible patterns (see Table 5). These codes have been systematically synthesised into the final code-set for the second pass (see Table 7).

Table 6: Initial Thematic Coding (Round 1)

CATEGORY	CODES
I. Personal & Professional Development	character development, Trust, willpower, discipline, Confidence, order, Empowerment, Cognitive adaptive skills, Education, career, Seeking for challenge
II. Military & Institutional	Military Drill, Military skill, Military care, Milit. tipps, authority, Ranks, BFT, recruitment, Marching and military tradition (pride), Kriegstüchtigkeit, Music corps, No-code
III. Group Dynamics & Social	teamwork, group cohesion, camaradeship, being proud, family, private life, Hobbies, Fitness, Food
IV. Gender & Representation	Gender normalisation, Women in leadership, underrepresentation, Being a role model (women -> visibility), Hairstyle, Period, Medical or care profession, Hip music, Light music

³¹ **Note:** Last access: 16.10.2025

³² **Note:** See for more about MAXQDA: <https://www.maxqda.com/> (Last Access: 23.10.2025)

Second Pass and Corpus Refinement: The entire final corpus was reviewed in the second pass to verify the code assignments and minimise potential miscoding. Similar codes were synthesised and merged to streamline the final interpretation (see Appendix III for details on merged codes). This process resulted in a final set of 16 analytical codes, including a “No-code” marker to identify content that needs to be excluded. The use of the “No-code” function to exclude content from the corpus is justified by the 5th (*Subject*) and 6th (*Women Recruitment Intent*) criterion for source selection (see Table 2). This led to a reduction of posts (Instagram: -76; TikTok: -5; YouTube: -28). The final analytical corpus, therefore, consists of (Instagram: *n*=44; TikTok: *n*=31; YouTube: *n*=27). Content has been excluded when there were only men or material visible. The web series *Save*³³ on YouTube was excluded as it was showing only civilian medical personnel in non-military settings. Textual slides, or pictures of military equipment that do not actively address women's recruitment, have been excluded as well. Yet most of the excluded content is still of explanatory value, as section (4.1) will show, since the method of FVNA also asks: “What is not shown in the image or video?”

Table 6: Coding Frequencies and Code Grouping for Discursive Tokenism (Round 2)

Code Group (Discursive Tokenism Effect)	Final Code Count
DT I: Visibility	55
DT II: Contrast	32
DT III: Assimilation Pressure	42
DT IV: Low Visibility	52
No-Code	186
DT Code Category (Rationale)	Sub-Code (Final Terms)
DT I: Visibility	Being a Role Model
(Heightened scrutiny focusing on a few tokens)	Women in Leadership
	Women in Technical Jobs
	Symbolic Function
	Women / Woman
DT II: Contrast	Feminine Attributes
(Exaggerating differences between tokens and the majority)	Family (+)
	Hobbies
	Abgrenzung ³⁴ Private Life
DT III: Assimilation Pressure	De-gendering (+)
(Pressure on tokens to conform to majority norms)	Military Skill
	Order (+)
	Hegemonic Attributes (+)
	Cognitive Skills
	Character Development

³³ <https://www.bundeswehrkarriere.de/save> (Last Access: 03.12.2025).

³⁴ **Note:** Boundary between Private and Professional Life

Code Group (Discursive Tokenism Effect)	Final Code Count
DT IV: Low Visibility	Underrepresentation
(Isolation and marginalisation of tokens)	Man / Men as Authority
	Aesthetic/Cultural Elements
No-Code	No-Code

Appendix II: Datasets³⁵

Appendix II³⁶ contains the supplementary raw dataset ($n = 1,179$), including the MAXQDA project file (“*MaxQDA Master Thesis Analysis_mqda*”) and the filtered dataset spreadsheet (“Appendix II”) used for analysis. The spreadsheet includes all relevant metadata, such as platform identifiers, timestamps, and direct links to the downloaded and analysed content.

All materials are accessible via the link and QR code provided below:

<https://osf.io/t3ajn>

³⁵**Note:** Content available at: Center For Open Science; “Open Science Framework” : <https://osf.io/t3ajn>

³⁶ Additional Information on Data handling:

- **Data Source:** All content is derived from publicly available data (TikTok, Instagram, YouTube). No sensitive or personal data was collected, aligning with GDPR principles.
- **Hosting:** Supplementary datasets are hosted on the Open Science Framework (OSF), a non-commercial, open-access research repository supporting transparent and reproducible scholarship, at <https://osf.io/t3ajn> (view-only access).
- **Usage Restriction:** The content is for academic review only. Commercial use, redistribution, or any attempt to re-identify data subjects is strictly prohibited.
- **Alternative Access:** If you cannot or choose not to use OSF services, please email the author at Julian.muxfeldt@posteo.de for a direct transfer.

Conflict of Interests:

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

Statement of Originality:

I declare that this thesis has been written independently, complying with the current regulations on the use of generative Artificial Intelligence (AI). Submitting AI-generated content as one's own content is considered plagiarism. No text or text fragment has been used for text production. If AI was involved, it was used within the limited purpose of text correction of grammar. Further, I declare that this thesis has never been used for any other purpose than obtaining a Master's Degree (M.Sc) in the War and Defence programme at the Swedish Defence University (Försvarshögskolan).³⁷

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Julian Muxfeldt; Stockholm, 07.01.2026

³⁷ **Note:** For more information, check the provided guidance's by the Swedish Defence University:

1. <https://www.fhs.se/en/student-web/all-about-your-studies/rights-and-responsibilities/cheating-and-plagiarism.html>
2. <https://www.fhs.se/en/student-web/all-about-your-studies/rights-and-responsibilities/guidance-on-ai.html>
3. <https://www.fhs.se/en/student-web/all-about-your-studies/support/academic-writing.html>
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(Last Access: 06.10.2025).